

Home sweet home: Effect of price changes on uptake and upcoding of GP home visits

Authors: *Jamie O'Halloran and Jonas Schreyögg*

ABSTRACT

Aim: This study aims to estimate GPs response to an increase in the fee size for home visits. We estimate whether the fee increase lead to an increase in number of home visits and whether the fee change lead to upcoding of the reported reimbursed travel distance.

Background: There is limited evidence on how physicians react to fee changes. We use a case study of Denmark. Danish GPs are paid predominantly through a fee-for-service based system (2/3rds of their income). In 2017 the fee for home visits increased on average by 157%. The changes in fee size is dependent on the travel distance for the home visit and is constructed using bands of distance. The travelled distance is self-reported by the GP.

Methods: The changes in the fee schedules affected all GPs. The intensity of treatment differs due to the differences in the time taken for GPs to travel to their patients. We are able to exploit that there is variation in travel time both across and within GPs. GPs that have lower travel times to their patients have a stronger financial incentive to conduct home visits as the revenue per minute is larger. Therefore, we use a quasi-difference-in-difference framework where we identify the impact of the price rise from an interaction between time in minutes to patient with a dummy indicating if the year is after the price rise. GPs have some discretion in reporting distance travelled as it is self-reported. Thus, GPs have an incentive to up code their travel distance as to move up in the fee schedules. To provide evidence of this, we measure whether the difference between actual travel distance and billed distance increases after the price rises. The analysis is conducted at the patient level (N= ~17,000,000) controlling for patient characteristics, GP characteristics and GP practice fixed effects.

Data: We use detailed administrative data at patient level from 2015 to 2018. A total of 3,500 GPs (in 2,200 practices) provide services to Danish residents. We use data from the National Health Service Register to determine of the GPs' provision of home visits to patients. The Health Care Organisational Register provides information on the GPs address. We map each patient's address to their GP's address using the Danish Address Register, which allows us measure actual distance travelled and the travel time so that we are able to compare billed and actual distance travelled. We use Statistics Denmark's registers to measure patient characteristics, i.e. their health state, education and income.

Results: Initial findings suggest that an increase in fee size increases GPs provision of home visits. Patients who have previously received a home visit seem to benefit the most from the increase in fee. We also find some evidence of upcoding of reported distances.